

Supplementary Information

CONSERVATION IMPLICATIONS OF GENETIC STRUCTURE IN THE NARROWEST ENDEMIC QUILLWORT FROM THE EASTERN AMAZON

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TABLES

Table S1: Individuals of *Isoetes cangae* used in genomic analyses with geographical coordinates and site location in the Amendoim lake (Fig. 1C). Missing data values (in percentage) and average coverage depth by individual after filtering steps (35,638 SNPs) are also provided.

Sample ID	Site	Longitude	Latitude	Missing Data (%)	Coverage
ITV20304	Center	-50.372	-6.399	0.091	124.75
ITV20305	Center	-50.372	-6.399	0.132	106.86
ITV20306	Center	-50.372	-6.399	0.160	91.43
ITV20307	Center	-50.372	-6.399	0.063	100.18
ITV20308	Center	-50.372	-6.399	0.110	96.83
ITV20309	Center	-50.372	-6.399	0.094	102.07
ITV20310	North	-50.371	-6.397	0.174	77.28
ITV20311	West	-50.372	-6.399	0.094	142.74
ITV20312	West	-50.372	-6.399	0.130	78.74
ITV20313	West	-50.372	-6.399	0.124	116.26
ITV20314	West	-50.372	-6.399	0.176	108.73
ITV20316	East	-50.371	-6.399	0.135	98.94
ITV20317	North	-50.371	-6.397	0.094	128.83
ITV20318	Center	-50.372	-6.399	0.207	91.15
ITV20319	Center	-50.372	-6.399	0.124	97.34
ITV20320	Center	-50.372	-6.399	0.171	93.12
ITV20321	Center	-50.372	-6.399	0.127	98.28
ITV20322	Center	-50.372	-6.399	0.138	90.50
ITV20323	Center	-50.372	-6.399	0.110	109.01

ITV20324	Center	-50.372	-6.399	0.074	104.61
ITV20331	West	-50.372	-6.399	0.317	48.36
ITV20332	West	-50.372	-6.399	0.165	94.57
ITV20333	West	-50.372	-6.399	0.127	88.05
ITV20334	West	-50.372	-6.399	0.171	76.96
ITV20335	North	-50.371	-6.397	0.171	73.39
ITV20336	North	-50.371	-6.397	0.196	77.05
ITV20337	North	-50.371	-6.397	0.204	65.94
ITV20338	North	-50.371	-6.397	0.187	76.26
ITV20339	East	-50.371	-6.399	0.110	94.04
ITV20340	East	-50.371	-6.399	0.298	56.58
ITV20341	East	-50.371	-6.399	0.174	77.57
ITV20342	East	-50.371	-6.399	0.226	69.67
ITV20343	South	-50.372	-6.402	0.336	44.23
ITV20344	South	-50.372	-6.402	0.287	57.30
ITV20345	South	-50.372	-6.402	0.201	69.24
ITV20346	South	-50.372	-6.402	0.223	68.50
ITV20347	North	-50.371	-6.397	0.402	47.86
ITV20348	North	-50.371	-6.397	0.309	54.93
ITV20349	North	-50.371	-6.397	0.232	78.15
ITV20350	North	-50.371	-6.397	0.182	77.32
ITV20351	North	-50.371	-6.397	0.245	62.31
ITV20352	North	-50.371	-6.397	0.108	83.28
ITV20353	North	-50.371	-6.397	0.243	58.83
ITV20354	South	-50.372	-6.402	0.143	80.45
ITV20355	South	-50.372	-6.402	0.149	99.02
ITV20356	South	-50.372	-6.402	0.312	52.39
ITV20357	South	-50.372	-6.402	0.198	68.05
ITV20358	South	-50.372	-6.402	0.149	86.92
ITV20359	South	-50.372	-6.402	0.292	49.90
ITV20360	East	-50.371	-6.399	0.171	77.67
ITV20361	East	-50.371	-6.399	0.389	50.00

ITV20362	East	-50.371	-6.399	0.256	70.69
ITV20363	East	-50.371	-6.399	0.085	113.89
ITV20364	East	-50.371	-6.399	0.121	117.11
ITV20365	East	-50.371	-6.399	0.113	85.41

Table S2: Minimum size (SIZE) in base pair (bp), number (N), total of base pair (TOTAL) of 30,000 selected contigs from the Genome Skimming approach for the samples of *I. cangae*.

SIZE (bp)	N	TOTAL (bp)
100	30,000	16,698,786
250	29,957	16,690,814
500	8,082	9,054,021
1,000	3,070	5,677,632
2,500	492	1,903,560
5,000	74	503,032
10,000	4	53,986

Table S3: Number of SNPs retained in each filtering step to select neutral SNPs. Variant calling returned the raw SNPs, quality filters are described in Material and Methods section and linkage disequilibrium filter was performed in two step, within the same contig and between contigs, in each one the value of $r^2 < 0.4$. Outliers SNPs for F_{ST} values were removed using sNMF in the last step. For details see Material and Methods section.

Filtering Steps	SNPs
Raw	2,349,431
Quality Filter	71,621
LD Filter (Within Contigs)	60,377
LD Filter (Between Contigs)	36,275
F_{ST} outliers (sNMF)	35,638

Table S4: Mean, upper and lower bound of confidence intervals (C.I. 95%) for effective population size (N_e) using linkage disequilibrium method (LD). Results from resampled datasets with different numbers of SNPs (from 5,000 to 30,000 SNPs) with no missing data are showed. Last column indicates the results using all neutral SNPs with missing data (35,638). ∞ = infinite.

Datasets	Lower	Mean	Upper
5,000	11,565.2	24,303.4	∞
10,000	24,832.4	56,707.5	∞
15,000	43,234.5	124,424.3	∞
20,000	45,246.2	92,715.8	∞
25,000	38,112.6	58,221.1	122,907.9
30,000	51,570.5	84,411.1	321,807.5
35,638	45,557.2	64,226.2	108,852.5

FIGURES:

Figure S1: Cross-entropy for sNMF with regularization parameter $\alpha=1000$ (A). We tested different values for α (10, 100, 500, 1000, 2000, 4000), all values showed the same pattern, $K = 1$ and $K=2$ with lower cross-entropy values, and we used $K = 2$ to select SNPs because for this analysis we need a $K \geq 2$. Adjusted p-values with a genomic inflation factor of 0.6 to remove more SNPs (B), and Manhattan plot (C) for F_{ST} outliers, showing in red the 637 SNPs removed in this filtering step.

Figure S2: Estimates for number of ancestry populations for different values of regularization parameter (α) in sNMF.

Figure S3: Estimates for number of genetic clusters for different numbers of principal components in DAPC.

Figure S4: Tukey's tests between five areas of the Amendoim lake showing significant mean differences in individual diversity metrics. Points represent the mean and bars the 95% confidence interval for each comparison. Pointed line indicate the 0, if the confidence intervals include the 0, the difference between mean is not significant. He_{obs} = observed heterozygosity; He_{exp} = expected heterozygosity; F_{IS} = inbreeding coefficient.

Figure S5: Pairwise comparisons between *Isoetes cangae* individuals for the Yang's relatedness coefficient (Rel), indicating relatedness values close to zero.